

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids: Part I. N-Aryl Hydroxamic Acids as Reagents for Vanadium(V)[†]

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An examination of the coloured complexes of 22 N-aryl hydroxamic acids with vanadium(V) in concentrated hydrochloric acid media has been made. The absorption spectra of these complexes have been determined and their molar absorptivities compared. The effects of attaching different substituent groups such as phenyl, naphthyl, furyl, and thienyl to the hydroxamic acid functional grouping, on the corresponding vanadium complexes have been discussed. In addition, the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium (V) with N-*p*-tolylcinnamohydroxamic acid, the most sensitive reagent among the hydroxamic acids, has been briefly described.

The use of N-*p*-tolyl-2-thenohydroxamic acid and N-phenyl-2-thenohydroxamic acid for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium has been described.¹ The high selectivity and sensitivity of these reagents for vanadium reaction and their other valuable analytical properties stimulated interest for undertaking a more comprehensive examination of this class of compounds. In this connection, a number of hydroxamic acids (I), in which R₁ and R₂ were replaced by a

variety of substituent groups, were synthesised² and their reactions with vanadium (V) in strongly acidic media examined. The absorption spectra of the coloured systems were determined and their molar absorptivities at the wavelengths of maximum absorption compared³. In this communication the results of these and other related investigations are recorded.

This study showed that among the 22 substituted hydroxamic acids examined here, N-*p*-tolylcinnamohydroxamic acid (trivial name *p*-TCHA) gave the most sensitive colour reaction with vanadium (V). This reagent also displayed somewhat better tolerance for the interfering ions. Hence, the results obtained in the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium (V) with this reagent are also briefly described.

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It may be noted that after the completion of this work³, a number of analogous N-aryl hydroxamic acids have been reported for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium (V).⁴⁻⁷

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Aryl hydroxamic acid were synthesised² and their 0.1% w./v. (0.005M approximately) solutions in ethyl alcohol-free chloroform were used for all extraction work. These solutions are stable for several days when stored in amber bottles.

An aqueous solution of ammonium meta vanadate (Hopkin and Williams AnalalR grade), whose vanadium content was determined volumetrically⁸, was used. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from reagent grade salts using the procedure of West⁹.

Ethyl Alcohol-free Chloroform. Ethyl alcohol was removed by washing the reagent grade chloroform five or six times with half its volume of water and drying over fused calcium chloride. It was distilled and stored in a cool place in amber bottles. This method of purification and storage proved satisfactory. Used chloroform was also recovered by this method.

Apparatus. Beckman Models DK-2 and DU spectrophotometers with two matched 10-mm silica or corex cells were employed for all photometric measurements.

Colour Reaction. The general behaviour of the hydroxamic acids in their reaction with vanadium (V) was similar to that of N-phenyl-2-theno-hydroxamic acid¹.

Oxidation State. The vanadium in the sample solution must be in the pentavalent state. The sample solution is, therefore, slightly acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and then treated with a few drops of dilute solution of potassium permanganate until a faint pink colour persists. Alternatively, the sample solution is treated with a few drops of bromine water, the excess of which is removed by boiling.

Prepare standard stock solutions of vanadium (V) containing approximately 0.002 to 0.02 mg of vanadium per ml. Transfer 10-ml. aliquots of the solutions into 100-ml. separating funnels. To each separating funnel, add 5 to 6 ml. of concentrated hydrochloric acid (Sp. Gr. 1.18) and 10 to 12 ml. (or more) of 0.1% w./v. chloroform solution of the hydroxamic acid, and shake the funnel vigorously. Allow the layers to separate for 2 minutes, and collect the chloroform layer in a small conical flask which contains about 1.5 grams of anhydrous sodium sulphate. Wash the aqueous layer two times with 5-ml. portions of chloroform to remove any residual colour, and add the washings to the contents of the conical flask. Decant the coloured solution from the conical flask into a 25-ml. volumetric flask, and wash out the adhering colour from the sodium sulphate with small portions of chloroform. Combine the washings with the main solution and dilute to mark.

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Record the spectra of the solutions, using appropriate compensating blank solutions (chloroform being used for all colourless reagents), with the help of an automatic ratio recording Beckman DK-2 spectrophotometer to locate the absorption band. Then measure the absorbance of all solutions at the wave length of maximum absorption using the manual Beckman DU spectrophotometer. Calculate the average molar absorptivity of the coloured system on the basis of vanadium content.

Similar studies were made with all hydroxamic acids, using the same stock solutions of vanadium. Tests were applied to the aqueous phase to check for the quantitative extraction of vanadium, and whenever necessary larger volumes of hydroxamic acid solution were employed. Coloured systems of all hydroxamic acids are stable for several days. For comparing the molar absorptivities of coloured extracts, following Sandell's recommendations²⁰, the solutions were so prepared that their absorbance fell between 0.2 and 0.7. In this range all coloured extracts obey Beer's law.

The results of this study are recorded in Table I, and the absorption spectra of a few typical coloured systems are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Absorption spectra of vanadium (V) complexes (4.69 mg. V/litre) extracted from 4N hydrochloric acid with chloroform containing

- (A) N-*p*-tolyleinnamohydroxamic acid,
- (B) N-Phenyleinnamohydroxamic acid,
- (C) N-*p*-Tolyl-2-thenohydroxamic acid,
- (D) N-Phenylbenzohydroxamic acid,
- (E) N-1-Naphthylbenzohydroxamic acid,
- (F) N-Phenyl-*m*-nitro-benzohydroxamic acid, and
- (G) N-Phenyl-3, 5-dinitro-benzohydroxamic acid.

Effect of alcohols. The effect of alcohols on the stability of chloroform extracts, obtained from strongly acidic media, were interesting. Addition of even a trace amount of ethyl alcohol brought about a change in colour from typical violet (or bluish violet) to reddish violet. The absorption band registered a hypsochromic and hypochromic effect. The change

in colour, and in the position and intensity of absorption band, continued for several hours or days (depending on the quantity of ethyl alcohol added) until the extracts finally became red, and the absorption band was considerably broadened. By adding large amounts of ethyl alcohol this change could be brought about almost instantaneously. Many other alcohols, both chloroform miscible and immiscible, such as methanols, propanols, butanols, pentanols, hexanols, octanols, glycol, glycerol, cyclohexanol, benzyl alcohol, and terpineol etc., exhibited a similar influence.

On account of this effect of alcohols, use of ethyl alcohol-free chloroform is recommended for all extraction studies.

Incidentally, it may be pointed out that preliminary experiments based on this observation have shown promise for developing a specific test for detecting alcohols. It is proposed to extend this investigation. Almost parallel behaviour of magenta coloured vanadium (V)-8-quinolinol system which turns red on the addition of alcohols, has already been utilised for detecting and determining alcohols¹⁰⁻¹¹.

DISCUSSION

The effects of attaching various substituent groups to the carbon and nitrogen atoms of the hydroxamic acid functional grouping, are prominently reflected in the spectral characteristics of the vanadium (V) complexes of the modified compounds. This is borne out by an examination of the data given in Table I for the complexes formed in strongly acidic solutions. The colours of the complexes vary from reddish-violet to bluish-violet, the position of absorption bands from 510 to 555 $m\mu$, and the molar absorptivities from 3,300 to 6,500 litres/mole cm.

The complexes of cinnamohydroxamic acids are conspicuous by their large molar absorptivities. They are bluish-violet, and their absorption bands appear at longer wave lengths. The introduction of thiophene ring in hydroxamic acid molecule also increases the molar absorptivities of the corresponding complexes but no such effect is noticed with furan ring.

Replacement of phenyl group by *p*-tolyl group (R_1) generally causes a slight hyperchromic and batho-chromic effect, while the introduction of negative substituents such as chloro, bromo and nitro- in phenyl group (R_2) results in a hypochromic effect; the effect being most pronounced with nitro-substitution. Conclusions on the effects of position of substituent groups may possibly be drawn if a sufficiently large number of such compounds are studied. It is noticed that chloro, bromo, and nitro substituted hydroxamic acids are unsuitable for solvent extraction because with them the full colour develops slowly and on repeated extraction. Some of the nitro substituted hydroxamic acids, which are themselves coloured, are unsuitable for colorimetric work because they show appreciable absorption at the wave lengths of maximum absorption of the corresponding vanadium complexes.

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TABLE I

Spectral Characteristics of Vanadium(V) -Hydroxamic Acid Colored Systems in Chloroform (From 4N HCl)

S. No.	Hydroxamic Acid	Color of Chloroform Extract	Wavelength of maximum Absorption, $m\mu$	Molar Absorptivity, at λ max.*
1	N-Phenylbenzo-	V	525	4,650 ^{12,13}
2	N- <i>p</i> -Tolylbenzo-	V	530	4,700
3	N-Phenyleinnamo-	BV	540	6,300 ¹⁴
4	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyleinnamo-	BV	555	6,500
5	N-Phenyl-2-theno-	V	530	5,450
6	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2-theno-	V	530	5,750
7	N-Phenyl-2-furo-	V	530	4,650
8	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2 furo	V	532	4,900
9	N-Phenyl-1-naphtho	BV	540	4,450
10	N-1-Naphthylbenzo	RV	515	4,450
11	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-1-naphtho	BV	545	4,650
12	N-Phenyl- <i>o</i> -methyl-benzo	BV	540	4,650
13	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -methyl-benzo	BV	535	4,800
14	N-Phenyl-3,5-dinitrobenzo-	RV	510	3,300
15	N-Phenyl- <i>o</i> -nitro-dinitrobenzo	V	525	4,100
16	N-Phenyl- <i>m</i> -nitro-benzo-	RV	515	3,600
17	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -nitro-benzo-	V	525	4,300
18	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -nitro-benzo-	V	530	4,500
19	N-Phenyl- <i>o</i> -chloro-benzo	V	525	4,300
20	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -chloro-benzo	V	525	4,500
21	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -chloro-benzo-	V	528	4,600
22	N-Phenyl- <i>m</i> -bromo-benzo-	V	525	4,300

V, Violet

BV, Bluish Violet

RV, Reddish Violet

* The average of at least 12 measurements on 4 samples of different concentrations.

As a result of the present and previous studies^{1,12-19}, a few broad concepts, which may prove valuable in examining new reagents from the family of hydroxamic acids, have developed. These are :

(i) When R_1 is hydrogen, the corresponding hydroxamic acids and their vanadium (V) complexes are practically not extracted with hydrocarbon and non-oxygenated solvents such as benzene, toluene, chloroform, and carbon tetrachloride. Water-immiscible solvents such as higher alcohols too are not efficient for extracting all complexes, especially those which are formed in strongly acidic media. Such reagents are, therefore, not likely to be of much practical value for developing colorimetric methods employing solvent extraction.

(ii) Replacement of R_2 by groups containing electrophilic substituents such as chloro, bromo, and nitro, introduces undesirable features both in the reagents and their vanadium(V) complexes. Syntheses of such reagents for solvent extraction and spectrophotometry will, therefore, be of little utility.

In future work it will be worthwhile to investigate the effects of following changes on the general behaviour of reagents and their metal complexes.

(i) To replace R_1 by groups containing electrophilic substituents such as fluoro, chloro, bromo, iodo, and nitro.

(ii) To further increase the length of conjugation by the introduction of larger number of side chain double bonds in the groups for R_2 .

Determination of Vanadium with N-p-Tolylcinnamohydroxamic acid. Vanadium is determined with *p*-TCHA by following basically the same procedure as in the case of N-*p*-tolyl-2-thenohydroxamic acid (*p*-TTHA)¹. Hence, only a brief description of the critical factors influencing its determination is given.

Acidity. The optimum range of hydrochloric acid concentration in the aqueous phase is between 2.7 and 7.5N. Only hydrochloric acid was suitable for adjusting the acidity, but the presence of other common mineral acids could be tolerated, provided that their concentration in the aqueous phase was less than 1N.

Amount of Reagent. Maximum development of colour takes place when the mole ratio of vanadium to reagent is 1 to 10. In practice, for each mg. of vanadium approximately 80 mg. of reagent were used. It may be noted that solid *p*-TCHA is pale green but its 0.1% w./v. solution has practically negligible absorption at 555 m μ . Hence, a large excess of reagent is tolerated. However, if necessary, the appropriate compensating blank solutions may be used in reference cell.

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Beer's Law. The optimum range for determining vanadium, based on Sandell's recommendations²⁰, is approximately 39 to 136 μg of the metal per 25 ml. of the solution.

Other Critical Factors. The presence of a side chain double bond in *p*-TCHA molecule makes this reagent more susceptible to attack by oxidising agents. Hence, only exact amounts of bromine water or potassium permanganate solution, required for oxidising vanadium to the pentavalent state, should be used. Temperature, ionic strength, and volume of the aqueous phase may vary within wide limits without any adverse effect on the colour development. The colour is extracted into the chloroform layer in about 2 minutes and is stable for several days.

Effects of Diverse Ions. In addition to the ions not interfering in the determination of vanadium with *p*-TTHA¹, zirconium (IV) did not interfere when *p*-TCHA was used as reagent. Besides, with *p*-TCHA as reagent a definite improvement in the tolerance for molybdenum (VI) and titanium(IV) was observed. A 20 to 1 weight ratio of each of these ions to vanadium (V) was tolerated.

Results obtained in a few typical determinations of vanadium are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Effects of Various Ions

(The concentration of vanadium present in each test was 101.9 μg . per 25 ml.)

Ion	Added as	Amount added, mg.	Absorbance, 555 $m\mu$	Amount of vanadium recovered, μg .
—	—	—	0.520	101.9
Al^{3+}	$\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	30	0.510	99.99
Co^{2+}	$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	30	0.530	103.9
Cu^{2+}	$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	30	0.515	100.9
Fe^{3+}	$\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	30	0.520	101.9
MoO_4^{2-}	Na_2MoO_4	5	0.480	94.0
MoO_4^{2-}	Na_2MoO_4	2	0.510	99.9
Mn^{2+}	$\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	30	0.515	100.9
Ti^{4+}	TiOCl_2	5	0.470	92.1
Ti^{4+}	TiOCl_2	2	0.505	99.0

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